

Temporal Coherence Loss due to Dynamic Scattering of Laser Light

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Abstract - The physical mechanisms which cause loss of coherence in scattered light are currently under investigation. It has been shown [1] that laser light scattered by a water column loses temporal coherence as a function of optical density. In this paper the results of measurement of the coherence loss due to radiative broadening are reported.

I. INTRODUCTION

An "ideal" laser operating at a single frequency would have an infinite coherence length. Real lasers emit light with a narrow frequency bandwidth and thus the coherence length is finite. A narrow spectral linewidth laser is considered a coherent source and may have a coherence length as large as several hundred meters. As laser light is scattered from particles in a volume of water the spectrum is broadened due to collisions between the particles, motion of the particles (Doppler), and absorption and re-emission (Rayleigh scattering). The decrease in coherence length can be quantified by recording the associated spectral broadening.

The overall goal for this research is to construct an interferometric imaging system which rejects scattered light. Since the coherence length of the scattered light is reduced, it should be possible to interferometrically discriminate between the scattered and unscattered light. Upon quantifying the coherence loss, interferometric systems can be designed to reject the scattered light (noise) and retain only the direct beam (signal) thus substantially increasing the signal-to-noise ratio for all types of active imaging systems. In general the coherence loss will be different for each laser and water sample, therefore each system would require specific inter-

ferometer parameters. In order to design and build interferometric imaging systems an understanding of the mechanisms causing the reduction in coherence length is necessary.

In Rayleigh or elastic scattering, a photon incident on an atom (or molecule) is absorbed and re-emitted in a single step process such that the absorbed and emitted photons are correlated. There is spectral broadening due to this scattering because of the finite linewidth of the excited state of the atom (molecule). Radiative transitions in the visible range are on the order of 10^{-7} to 10^{-9} seconds depending on the type of atom (molecule). These time scales are particularly amenable to Fabry-Perot spectrometry which can be used for processes in the range of $\sim 10^{-6}$ to $\sim 10^{-12}$ sec.

We report here measurements of the broadening of the power spectrum of a single mode of an argon-ion laser as the scattering media was varied. The light was expanded and collimated to pass through a tank of water and then refocused and transmitted to a Fabry-Perot spectrometer. The power spectrum of the laser line was digitized and the data were processed to obtain the coherence length. The results presented are measurements of the coherence length as a function of optical density of the water as diatomaceous earth was added.

Experiments are currently underway to measure the spectral broadening at frequencies above and below those resolvable with the Fabry-Perot spectrometer. Broadening in these regions should be associated with collisional and Doppler broadening respectively. At the completion of these experiments, the dominant mechanisms which cause the coherence loss will be isolated and further studied.

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II. BACKGROUND

The coherence length of light can be determined if either the autocorrelation function or the power spectrum is known.

The autocorrelation function of the optical field $E(t)$ is written

$$\Gamma(\tau) = \langle E^*(t)E(t+\tau) \rangle. \quad (1)$$

$\Gamma(\tau)$ is also the Fourier transform of the power spectrum, $I(\omega)$, of the light field which is given by

$$\Gamma(\tau) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{-i\omega\tau} I(\omega) d\omega. \quad (2)$$

The *degree of coherence* is defined as the normalized correlation function

$$\chi(\tau) = \frac{\Gamma(\tau)}{\Gamma(0)} = \frac{\langle E^*(t)E(t+\tau) \rangle}{\langle |E(t)|^2 \rangle} \quad (3)$$

where $\chi(\tau) = 1$ corresponds to perfect coherence and $\chi(\tau) = 0$ corresponds to total incoherence. In terms of the power spectrum

$$\chi(\tau) = \frac{\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{-i\omega\tau} I(\omega) d\omega}{\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} I(\omega) d\omega}. \quad (4)$$

The coherence time can be defined as [2]

$$\tau_c = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |\chi(\tau)|^2 d\tau \quad (5)$$

and the coherence length is then $l_c = c\tau_c$. Because of the Fourier transform relationship between the power spectrum and the autocorrelation function, if the width of the power spectrum broadens, the autocorrelation function narrows and the coherence length decreases.

III. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

An experiment was designed to measure the power spectrum of laser light passing through air and water using a Fabry-Perot spectrometer. The laser was an argon-ion gas laser [Ion Laser Technology model 5490ASF] operating in a single longitudinal mode at $514nm$ and with a bandwidth of $3MHz$. The frequency range investigated was from $1.5MHz$ to $10GHz$. This was accomplished with two different spectrometers each with a different resolution. The Fabry-Perot interferometer contains an etalon (cavity) of length d with partially reflecting spherical mirrors. Only light which satisfies $m\lambda/2 = d$ survives inside the cavity. The spectrum is scanned by piezoelectrically moving one of the mirrors

(changing d). The instrumental bandwidth gives the narrowest signal which can be resolved. The *free spectral range* (FSR) is the maximum change in frequency (mirror spacing) before the next spectral order is reached (m increments by one) and the signal repeats itself. The FSR is therefore the maximum change in frequency which can be measured with a given instrument. The finesse of the cavity is defined as the FSR divided by the instrumental bandwidth. Two Fabry-Perot spectrometers were used in this experiment. One had an instrumental bandwidth of $50MHz$ and a FSR of $10GHz$. This means that even though the laser had a bandwidth of about $3MHz$, the instrument showed a bandwidth of $50MHz$, the minimum resolvable for this spectrometer. The second spectrometer had an instrumental bandwidth of $1.5MHz$ and a FSR of $300MHz$. The overall range of measurement was therefore $1.5MHz$ to $10GHz$.

A top view of the experimental setup is shown in Fig. 1. After reflecting from mirror M_1 , the laser beam was expanded and collimated using a Newport T28-100 beam expander. After the light passed through the tank, it was collected and passed to the Fabry-Perot spectrometer using an identical beam expander in the reversed orientation (a beam compressor). The signal from the spectrometer was input to a digital oscilloscope and the digitized trace was transferred to a computer over a GPIB-IEEE interface. The data were then processed by first performing a FFT to obtain the autocorrelation function as in (2). The data were then squared and integrated to obtain the coherence time as in (5). The coherence time was multiplied by the speed of light to yield the coherence length and the coherence length was then plotted as a function of optical density.

The procedure to test for a change in the coherence length due to the presence of scattered light was identical for both spectrometers. With the tank empty (full of air) the power spectrum of the light, $I(\omega)$, was recorded. The tank was then filled with filtered ($2\mu m$) deionized water and $I(\omega)$ was again recorded. Successive measurements of $I(\omega)$ were recorded after adding measured amounts of diatomaceous earth (DE) (increments of 25, 50 or 100mg). The DE was maintained in suspension by four magnetic stirrers placed in the bottom of the tank and controlled from underneath the tank. After a complete set of measurements of $I(\omega)$ were investigated using one Fabry-Perot, the tank was emptied and cleaned and the procedure was repeated for the second spectrometer.

Fig. 1 Setup for coherence experiment with Fabry-Perot spectrometer.

The appropriate dependent variable for the experiment expressing the relative increase in scattering as DE is added is the optical density (OD). Data were taken for a fixed optical path length through water of 1.2m. The equation governing the extinction of a laser beam traversing an optical path in water is given by

$$I = I_0 e^{-cz} \quad (6)$$

where I is the intensity at an optical path length of z , I_0 is the intensity at $z=0$, and c is the extinction coefficient also called the beam attenuation coefficient. The properties of c depend on the number and type of suspended particles in the water and the wavelength of the light. The product cz is called the optical density (OD). The OD is a dimensionless quantity that gives the overall extinction of the beam. All data were taken as a function of OD by simultaneously measuring the beam attenuation coefficient, c , with a transmissometer operating at 514nm.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Spectral broadening was not observed using the first spectrometer in the range between 50MHz and 10GHz. Broadening was observed with the second spectrometer in the range between 1.5 and 300MHz. Each spectral trace was recorded ten times and the average coherence length calculated. Fig. 2 is a sample of the power spectrum for the beam passing through the empty tank. Fig. 3 is the square of the Fourier transform (i.e. the autocorrelation function) of the power spectrum in Fig. 2. The full width at half maximum (FWHM) of the spectrum was approximately 2.7MHz and the coherence length (l_c) was found to be 22+/-3m. Figs. 4 and 5 are the same as Figs. 2 and 3 for clear water in the tank. In

this case the FWHM was 3.5MHz and l_c was 17+/-3m. Fig. 6 is the power spectrum taken in cloudy water and Fig. 7 is it's squared autocorrelation function.

Fig. 2. Power spectrum of laser in air versus frequency.

Fig. 3. Squared autocorrelation function of laser in air versus time.

The FWHM of the spectrum in Fig. 6 is 8.3MHz and l_c is 4.2+/-0.8m. Note that the power spectrum broadens from air to cloudy water while the autocorrelation function narrows, thus giving a smaller coherence length as the water gets increasingly murky. The power spectra are all centered at zero in our plots and should really be offset to the frequency of the laser (approximately $6 \times 10^{14} \text{ Hz}$). However in the case of the power spectrum, the width is of interest and in the case of the squared autocorrelation function, the area under the curve is the critical parameter. In neither case is the result affected by an offset.

Power spectra of the laser in water were gathered over the range in OD from .048 (clear water) to 2.76 (875mg DE added to approximately 250 liters of water) and the results are plotted in Fig. 8. The large error in l_c for small values of OD is because the narrowness of the spectra is very near the instrumental limits of the spectrometer. The error in l_c is from the standard deviation of the data while the error in OD is the transmissometer instrumental error, +/-5%. Systematic errors in the value of OD may result from imperfect mixing of the DE and thus the actual OD may be smaller or larger than the average measured by the transmissometer.

Fig. 4. Power spectrum in clear water versus frequency.

Fig. 5. Squared autocorrelation function of laser in clear water versus time.

Fig. 6. Power spectrum in cloudy water versus frequency.

Fig. 7. Squared autocorrelation function of laser in cloudy water versus time.

Fig. 8. Coherence length as a function of optical density.

V. CONCLUSIONS

The broadening of a single mode of an argon-ion laser was measured after transmission through a scattering medium. The collected light was a combination of light transmitted without scattering and light primarily forward scattered into the collection optics. Thus it is expected that the measured broadening is in fact a convolution of the direct beam transmission function (unbroadened) and the forward scattered transmission function (broadened).

In more typical Rayleigh scattering experiments, [3] the broadening of the Rayleigh peak upon scattering from a single species is observed at a scattering angle of 90° relative to the transmitted beam. In those systems it is clear that all collected light is scattered. The width of the Rayleigh scattered light has been shown [4] to be proportional to $\kappa/\rho_o c_p$, where κ is the thermal conductivity, ρ_o is the equilibrium number density and c_p is the specific heat at constant pressure of the fluid. This broadening in pure fluids is essentially associated with density fluctuations at constant pressure and their associated thermal damping. With the addition of DE, the system becomes significantly more complex. Much work has been

done using quasi-elastic light scattering spectroscopy to measure the collective fluctuations of colloidal polystyrene spheres in aqueous solutions [5]. This work generally probes much slower processes than are measured in this experiment. More complete analysis of the broadening mechanisms for the Rayleigh line(s) in this system are forthcoming.

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